

RELEVANCE OF BUDDHA'S TEACHINGS IN PRESENT ERA

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ABSTRACT

Religion is an integral part of society. It is very difficult to imagine a society without religion. Religion provides discipline, morality, peace and stability in the society. There have been many religions from ancient times to the present times, in which many changes took place over time. If we talk about Buddhism, then Buddhism is the only religion in which human beings have been considered as the focal point. The sole purpose of Buddhism is to end the sufferings of human beings and pave the way for Nirvana. Buddha dharma means bringing discipline and inner tranquillity into our minds. Therefore, when we talk about transforming our mind and developing inner qualities, the only way we can do this is to utilize the mind itself. Buddha dharma is an instrument for training the mind-something we use to try to work out the problems that we all experience; problems that originate mainly at the mental level. In the present age, there is a need for a religion that harmonizes humanistic, worldly and spiritual tendencies. Buddhism is the best religion from all these perspectives. Buddhism is a religion based on the scientific view, so its usefulness increases more in present times. Due to the intellectual and scientific view of Buddhism, the spread of Buddhism can be seen not only in some countries but in the whole world. Buddhism is the only life-oriented religion. It is not a sin but a message of freedom from sorrow. Buddhism is not an extra terrestrial religion beyond the life, it is a practical religion of life.

Keywords : Buddhism and his relevance, Humanity, Nirvana, Gautam Buddha

In every era, 'religion' has been considered an essential part of society. Religion has a major contribution to establishing a civilized society. Religion provides purity and peace to man spiritually and mentally and makes man live by the moral upliftment of society. Therefore, one can say that religion is the method of human's moral uplift and betterment through which a welfare society can be built on the comprehensive development of man.

If we talk about India, then many religions have originated from ancient times to present times. Every religion has its own ideology and beliefs. All persons belonging to a religion follow the same ideology and beliefs. From various ancient texts, we get knowledge of contemporaneous religions and religious ideology. Hinduism, Vaishnavism, Shaivism is some of the oldest

religions practiced in society. Whose description is derived from Vedas and Puranas. Human welfare has been considered the focal point of all religions. But over time, religions have been rising and falling due to some errors being included in the religions. In the later Vedic period, due to the involvement of many rituals and rhetoric in Hinduism, many malpractices had emerged in the society. Due to which the life of a large community of society became painful. These circumstances resulted in the emergence of dissenting opinions in the sixth century B.C. . In which idol worship, rituals, superstitions and fanatics were opposed and paved the way for human welfare. The most prominent of these views is Buddhism. Which was not only spread in India but spread all over the world.

Buddhism originated in the sixth century B.C.,

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with its founder Gautama Buddha. Gautama Buddha was born in 563 B.C. in Kapilvastu, the capital of Shakya Gana, under a shawl tree in a beautiful forest called Lumbini. His father Shuddhodana was the chief of Shakya and his mother's name was Mahamaya. When Siddhartha was born, astrologers predicted that Prince Siddhartha would abandon these monarchical pleasures and find his way in the materialistic world. Siddhartha was of a reclusive and compassionate nature from childhood. He was filled with compassion seeing the sorrows of the world and wondered how a man can get rid of these sorrows. Seeing the nature of Siddhartha, father Shuddhodana brought Siddhartha with great pleasure and luxury. At the age of 16, Siddhartha was married to the most beautiful princess Yashodhara of Kolia Gan of Ramgram. After a few years of marriage, they had a son named Rahul. Even after this, Siddhartha's mind did not stay in the family. One day Siddhartha went out for a tour in his chariot, on the way he saw a patient, an old man, a deceased and a sanyasi, seeing whom Siddhartha became aware of the truth of the world. His mind drifted from worldly pleasures. He decided to leave the world to find the mysteries of life. One night while Yashodhara and Rahul were sleeping, he left the house and headed towards the forest, this incident is called 'Mahabhinishkramana'.¹ Siddhartha started harsh penance in the forest, even after many years of penance, he did not get peace of mind. Desiring to immerse life, he pledged and sat under the peepal tree of Bodhgaya. He attained enlightenment in the first Yama of the seventh night by continuously meditating. He realized that he had woken up from Maha-Mohanidra. This incident is called 'Sambodhi'. Siddhartha attained the position of 'Buddha' at this time, when he became a complete Buddha, at that time he was 36 years old.

Buddha did not give much emphasis on spiritual development in Buddhism but paid more attention to morality or modesty. All the preaching, teachings of Mahatma Buddha were very practical and prudent, which greatly influenced the public. Describing his teaching method, he has said, "Just as the depth of the sea grows silently, not suddenly, O monks, similarly, the teaching of this religion should be perpetual, you can only qualify by

step by step".²

In Buddhism the supreme authority are the words uttered by Shakyamuni. Therefore, the teaching of Buddhism must be the teaching that is closely linked to and intimate with the realities of our everyday life; otherwise, it will but fail in inspiring the human mind from its very depth's toward a belief in the teachings. In this sense, for the teaching to be one that we can make our own, it is desirable to be plain and simple, impartial in its quality, sufficient in representing the whole and yet accurate and familiar in the words that are used in our daily life.³

The teaching of the buddha:-

What Buddhists mean by law or dharma is the truth discovered by the Buddhas during their enlightenment and preached by them or their disciples during their public ministry.⁴ The word of the Buddha is good at the beginning, in the middle and at the end, perfect as to the meaning and the letter, homogenous, complete and pure.⁵ From the night of the enlightenment until the night of the Nirvana, all that the Buddha declared and taught is true and not false.⁶ The sky will fall down with the moon and stars, the ground will rise up to the heavens together with the mountains and forests, the ocean will dry up, but the great sages do not speak falsely. The Good word of the Buddhas has four features: it is well-spoken, agreeable and pleasant, and confirms what is beneficial and truthful.⁷

What place does the Buddha occupy about the Law which he discovered and preached and what are the main points of his teaching? We have seen that in the first explanation which 'Gautama gave of his system he laid down the 'Four Noble Truths' concerning Sorrow, its Cause, its Suppression, and the Path leading to its extinction, Briefly explained, these four Truths come to this:

1. That (those events which are distinctive of individual existence, such as) birth, the Five Skandhas, decay, disease, death, and (those which bring forcibly into mind the sense of separate existence, such as) contact with disagreeable objects, separation from pleasant ones, unfulfilled desire of possession,— are precisely those states

which are full of suffering or sorrow.

2. The kind of craving excitement, which follows on sensation, and causes the delusion of self and the lust of life—creating either delight in the objects that present themselves, or an eager desire to supply a felt want—this eager yearning thirst (Trishna, Pali tanha) growing into sensuality, the desire of future life, or love of the present world, is the origin of all suffering.
3. Sorrow and suffering will be overcome, extinguished, if this 'thirst' be quenched, this lust of life destroyed. "He who overcomes this contemptible thirst (difficult to be conquered in this world), sufferings fall off from him, like water drops from a lotus leaf.
4. To accomplish this end there is only one way,—the 'Noble Path' of a virtuous and thoughtful life: "Enter on this Path and make an end of sorrow: verily the Path has been preached by me, who have found out how to quench the darts of grief. You yourselves must make the effort: the Buddhas are only preachers: the thoughtful who enter the Path are freed from the bondage of the deceiver, Mara. And this means of salvation is not a mere vague admonition to 'be good'; it is worked out into detail, expressed in the Eight Divisions and Four Stages.

The Eight Divisions are as follows:-

1. Right views.
2. Right aims.
3. Right words.
4. Right behaviour.
5. Right mode of livelihood.
6. Right exertion.
7. Right mindfulness.
8. Right meditation and tranquillity.⁸

The teachings provided by Buddha are priceless and unforgettable. Buddha paved the way for man to follow which man should be able to save not only himself but also other humans related to him. This path provided by Buddha is called 'Madhyam Marg'. Even after extremely painful penance, when Buddha did not attain enlightenment, then Buddha concluded that the attainment of ultimate happiness is neither possible from

the extreme of worldly pleasures nor by extreme hard penance, liberation from the cycle of birth and death in this world, This is possible only if both these extras are discarded and the madhyam marg is adopted. Thus Buddha propounded the madhyam marg. The madhyam marg is based on precision. The Madhyam Marg is as relevant in the present era as it was in the time of the Buddha. Explain the middle way in a statement, according to Buddha, the string of the veena should not be pulled so much that it breaks or it should not be left so loose that it does not make a sound.

The madhyam marg emphasizes rationality, negating orthodoxy. In the present time, many types of contradictions are arising in the whole world. Any person, country or institution, is trying to prove himself to be the best. Therefore, the problems that are occurring all over the world, it is possible to solve most of these problems by madhyam marg displayed by Buddha. The madhyam marg motivates man for morality and virtue, he ends the evil inside man and develops virtues.

The relevance in the present era:-

The teaching of Buddhism is as relevant today as it was 2500 years ago. Buddhism indeed originated at a time when many errors had arisen in the contemporaneous religion and the common man was leading a very painful life. But Buddhism did not originate only to solve the problems of that time, but Buddhism emerged as a religion that can illuminate the whole world with its light of knowledge in every age and could encourage to choose the best path to follow it.

According to Dalai lama; Buddha dharma is an instrument for training the mind—something we use to try to work out the problems that we all experience; problems that originate mainly at the mental level. Negative emotional forces create mental unrest, such as unhappiness, fear, doubt, frustration and so forth; these negative mental states then cause us to engage in negative activities, which in turn bring us more problems and more suffering. Practicing Dharma is a way of working out these problems, be they long-term or immediate. In other words, Dharma protects us from unwanted suffering.

Buddha dharma means bringing discipline and inner tranquillity into our minds. Therefore, when we talk

about transforming our mind and developing inner qualities, the only way we can do this is to utilize the mind itself. There is nothing else we can use to bring about such change. Thus, we should realize that much of what we do not desire—unwanted events, unhappiness and suffering—come about as a result of our mistaken way of looking at the world and our destructive thoughts and emotions. These negative minds create both immediate unhappiness and future suffering as well.

To be able to dispel the suffering and undesirable events in our lives, we must first recognize what the negative and positive aspects of the mind are and be able to distinguish between them. Once we develop a clear understanding of the negative aspects of the mind and their destructive potential, the wish to distance ourselves from them will arise naturally within us. Similarly, when we recognize the positive aspects of the mind and its potential benefit, we will naturally aspire to gain and enhance these mental qualities. Such transformation of mind cannot be imposed on us from the outside but happens only based on voluntary acceptance and great enthusiasm inspired by a clear awareness of the benefits to be gained.⁹

At present, man is so much influenced by the people or institutions around him that he has forgotten to listen to the voice of his inner being. Man is trying to prove himself the best every time. Due to which jealousy, anger, sorrow, etc., indifferent feelings arise in him, that he does not know. Due to which man is getting away from his real happiness, in such a way, the teachings of Buddha show the path to man, by following which man can get real happiness. In his last words to his disciples, the Buddha said: "Make of yourself a light. Rely upon yourself: do not depend upon anyone else. Make my teachings your light. Rely upon them: do not depend upon any other teaching. Consider your body: Think of its impurity. Knowing that both its pain and its delight are alike causes of suffering, how can you indulge in its desires? Consider yourself; think of its transiency; how can you fall into delusion about it and cherish pride and selfishness, knowing that they must all end in inevitable suffering? Consider all substances; can you find among them any enduring 'self'? Are they not all aggregates that

sooner or later will break apart and be scattered? Do not be confused by the universality of suffering, but follow my teaching, even after my death, and you will be rid of the pain."¹⁰

In the present age, there is a need for a religion that harmonizes humanistic, worldly and spiritual tendencies. Buddhism is the best religion from all these perspectives. Buddhism is a religion based on the scientific view, so its usefulness increases more in present times. The 'Pratytyasamutpad theory' of Buddhism considers causalism to be the basis of all activities happening in the world. In the same science, the principle of causation has been considered as the basis of every phenomenon. Both science and Buddhism come to the same conclusion that there is no creator of creation. The principle of conservation of matter and energy in science says that matter or physical elements and energy can neither be created nor destroyed, they only transform. Buddhists fully agree with this and apply this principle to the mind as well. In Buddhism, "Chitta" means to be cognizant of events — conscious or unconscious, and the recognition of events can neither be created nor destroyed, it only transforms. In this way, rebirth is the transformation of the continuum of cognizance to a person's events, that is on the physical basis through another body.¹¹ According to the Dalai Lama, Buddhism is also based on logic like quantum physics, so Buddhism can also be called science. Quantum physics also talked about the disparity between appearance and reality as is said in Buddhism.

Due to the intellectual and scientific view of Buddhism, the spread of Buddhism can be seen not only in some countries but in the whole world. Today the situation in the world is the same as it was before the appearance of Lord Buddha. Mankind suffered terribly from casteism, inequality, ambiguity, poverty, varna system. Today again man has become the enemy of man, violence is resorted to overtake each other. One country has become the enemy of another country. Clouds of war keep hovering daily. Today the whole world wants peace. The only way to fulfill this desire for peace is not seen elsewhere in the universal religion. Today it is the call of the times that any religion can survive only by staying as prestigious as the universal religion. The German

philosopher Nötse's statement is true that “In the philosophical perspective, Buddhism is the only life-oriented religion. It is not a sin but a message of freedom from sorrow. Buddhism is not a extra terrestrial religion beyond the life, it is a practical religion of life”.

Buddha himself says My disciples, the teachings that I have given you are never to be forgotten or abandoned. They are always to be treasured, they are to be thought about, they are to be practiced. If you follow these teachings you will always be happy. The point of the teachings is to control your own mind. Keep your mind from greed, and you will keep your behavior right, your mind pure and your words faithful. By always thinking about the transiency of your life, you will be able to resist greed and anger, and will be able to avoid all evils.¹²

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